

Ethical, legal, social issues and scientific misconduct brought about by One Health in the realm of Open Science and Citizen Science in India- An exploratory mixed-methods study

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A. Abstract

Introduction: Open Science is the measure taken to accelerate responsible conduct of research in scientific advancements, making the data easily accessible to all citizens. On account of the lack of aiding policies and low institutional capacities for One Health (OH) in India, we anticipate a wide range of scientific misconduct in OH. Citizen Science deals with the general public's involvement in scientific research to solve concrete problems in society. Therefore, incorporating both Open Science and Citizen Science into OH would form a solid basis for ensuring research integrity in OH research.

Objectives: To identify the challenges and opportunities in OH in the realm of Open Science and Citizen Science through a scoping review of literature. Next, to explore the perceptions of various stakeholders about scientific misconduct and inequities brought about by Open Science and Citizen Science in OH. Finally, to map the grey areas and develop a framework to accelerate ethics and research integrity in OH through Open Science, and Citizen Science.

Methods: This is a non-interventional study with three phases- first, a scoping review with critical analysis; the second, a mixed method design (qualitative and quantitative). Third, to develop a framework to incorporate Open Science and Citizen Science into OH. The proposal is registered in advance in the Open Science Framework (OSF) registry <https://osf.io/e7x3z/>. The study was approved by the Yenepoya Ethics Committee-2 (YEC2/2023/044).

Conclusion: Based on the analysis of phases 1 and 2, we will develop a framework to incorporate ethics and research integrity through Open Science, and Citizen Science considerations, into OH. This will comprehensively facilitate scientific research, by considering the interdependence of science, ethics, and society in India and globally.

B. Background

Over the past decade, the global rise of zoonotic diseases has led most countries to adopt the One Health (OH) approach, promoting collaboration among stakeholders at the human-animal-environment interface. (1,2) Despite this, data sharing within OH is not always implemented. (3) Ribeiro et al (4) in their systematic review of 2019, identified challenges such as insufficient training in collaborative approaches, uneven resource distribution, and limited publishing platforms. Furthermore, Kullenberg and Kasperowski (5) highlighted public participation in epidemiological research under Citizen Science. In low-middle-income countries like India, limited funding complicates the practice of Open Science and Citizen Science, leading to

potential inequities and exploitation. A major obstacle is the lack of access to shared information. Therefore, it is crucial to explore the ethical issues in applying Open Science and Citizen Science within OH to guide the community in these practices, promoting ethics and research integrity.

Relevance and importance to society

This project will contribute to sustainable social development by enhancing research integrity and ethics in public health research. It aims to build society's trust through community engagement, transparency, and data sharing. As India is in the early stages of implementing the OH approach, the study will guide OH researchers and policymakers in adopting best practices for open data sharing via Open Science and Citizen Science. This will contribute to sustainable social development not only in India but also in other low- and middle-income countries.

Research Questions

1. What are the opportunities and challenges at the interfaces of OH, Open Science, Citizen Science, society, and policy?
2. What are the spectrum of scientific misconduct and inequities brought about by Open Science and Citizen Science in OH?

Objectives

1. To identify the opportunities and challenges in OH in the realm of Open Science and Citizen Science from a comprehensive review of literature
2. To explore the spectrum of scientific misconduct and inequities brought about by Open Science and Citizen Science in OH as perceived by the stakeholders.
3. To identify the grey areas, and accelerate ethics and research integrity in OH through Open Science and Citizen Science.

C. Methods

Study duration: July 2024- May 2026

Phase 1: Scoping review (ongoing)

Inclusion and exclusion of articles: Original articles on Open Science, Citizen Science, and OH published in the last 10 years (2014-2024)

Databases: PubMed, Embase, Medline, Global health

Search terms: One Health AND Open Science, Citizen Science, volunteer monitoring, Open data, ethics

Articles will be screened on Covidence and coded with NVivo 14. The search results and inclusion process will be presented in a PRISMA-ScR flow diagram.

Phase 2: Qualitative and quantitative study

a. Qualitative study

The study will be conducted in India with the stakeholders identified by snowball sampling technique. The first participant will be selected from Yenepoya University, Mangalore, India followed by 25 or until information saturation. The same sampling technique will be used for the quantitative phase.

Inclusion criteria: Stakeholders conducting OH research in India in the last three years - Epidemiologists, Veterinarians, Ecologists, Citizen Scientists and policymakers.

Exclusion criteria: Participants who have not conducted any public health research in India.

Tool: Interviews will follow a validated semi-structured schedule, with written informed consent obtained from participants. The recordings will be then transcribed and coded using NVivo 14.

b. Quantitative study: Questionnaire-based survey

Tool: 15-item semi-structured questionnaire

Sample Size: 87, calculated based on 63% supporting OH in a previous European survey (6), with 5% significance and 10% margin of error.

Analysis: Descriptive and summary measures, Chi-square and non-parametric tests.

Phase 3: Ethical reflections (Normative theory)

Method: To analyze phases 1 and 2 within Indian Council of Medical Research guidelines-ICMR, 2017 (7), and develop a framework to incorporate ethics and research integrity into OH through Open Science and Citizen Science.

E. References:

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